

Research Article

Integrating Water Level Monitoring in Reservoir Tanks for Effective Water Management, Risk Mitigation, and Safety in Plant Control Systems Course

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Abstract: This study investigates the integration of water level monitoring in reservoir tanks to improve water management, mitigate risks, and enhance safety within plant control systems. A semi-automated control system, utilizing Arduino microcontrollers and ultrasonic sensors, was designed to maintain accurate water levels while reducing operational inefficiencies and hazards. Experimental results revealed that the semi-automated approach significantly reduced the time required for tank filling and draining from 5 and 6 minutes, respectively, to just 1 minute and 38 seconds each. This advancement eliminated risks associated with manual handling, such as wet floors and slipping hazards, and promoted a safer working environment. Furthermore, the system minimized water waste and enhanced resource conservation, contributing to sustainable laboratory practices. The proposed system demonstrates considerable potential for application in industrial and educational settings, where it not only enhances operational efficiency but also fosters a culture of safety and environmental responsibility. These findings emphasize the importance of integrating innovative control systems to address contemporary challenges in water management and plant operations.

Keywords: Water management; Risk assessment; Safety.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Water waste is a significant threat to the environment in laboratory operations because several processes, such as washing glassware, cooling equipment, and chemical reactions, require considerable water. Uncontrolled water use raises operating expenses, depletes resources, and, if improperly disposed of, can harm the environment. For example, excessive rinse methods or continuous-flow systems might consume significantly more water than is necessary, and improper wastewater treatment can discharge pollutants into the environment. Reducing laboratory water waste and the environmental impact of scientific research can be achieved by putting into practice effective water management techniques.

Water management in the lab is vital for operational effectiveness and environmental sustainability. For cooling, rinsing, and diluting, laboratories frequently need enormous volumes of water. If this isn't closely monitored, it can lead to excessive waste and expensive utility expenses. Effective water management minimizes the risk of pollutant discharge into ecosystems and conserves

this essential resource, which lessens the environmental impact of scientific activities. Additionally, encouraging researchers to use only what is necessary, it fosters a culture of responsible science. Furthermore, adopting sustainable practices—like recirculating cooling systems, low-flow fixtures, and water recycling when practical—helps a lab lower its carbon footprint and match its operations with more general sustainability objectives, which is advantageous for the environment and the institution.

In laboratory settings, the water level control experiment provides beneficial hands-on learning opportunities that link the theoretical and practical components of control systems. Through practical water level manipulation in a controlled tank setting, students learn important ideas in process dynamics, feedback control, and disturbance rejection. This experience is essential for students studying mechanical and plant control, where they must learn how to calibrate equipment, adjust parameters, and watch how systems react to changes in real-time. While handling variations in water levels brought on by outside influences, students can improve their skills in reaction time analysis, proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller adjustment, and troubleshooting by simulating disturbances like oscillatory loads or step shifts (Urrea & Páez, 2021). Research indicates that these trials enhance students' comprehension of process modeling and system stability, which are critical abilities for both academic and industrial settings.

Experiments with water level control are useful for comprehending process dynamics, but if water use is not controlled properly, they may cause environmental problems. Significant water waste can happen in open-loop systems without water recycling, especially in big labs that run continuously. Particularly in areas where water resources are scarce, this usage adds to resource depletion and puts further demand on them. Furthermore, incorrect experimental water disposal might result in pollution and negative environmental effects, particularly if the water is combined with chemicals.

By highlighting the effective use of water, laboratory water level control studies support sustainable resource management. Closed-loop systems, which reduce water waste and promote recycling, are used in many experiments. This enables students to learn resource conservation while studying control systems (Iskandar, et al., 2019). In industrial settings where water conservation is essential, this approach supports more general sustainability objectives. In addition to teaching feedback management and disturbance rejection, these lab tasks inspire aspiring engineering teams to use environmentally friendly practices in their work.

During a recent water level control lab exercise, there was an event when water splashed onto the floor as the tank was being filled and drained. Water splashed throughout the setup area as a result of a tiny leak caused by a misaligned hose connection when water was poured into the tank. High water flow rates throughout the drainage process resulted in splashing close to the drain, which made the floor slick. Although there were no injuries, the event made clear the necessity of more stringent water-handling procedures since wet floors raise the risk of slips and falls (National Safety Council [NSC], 2021). According to research, mitigating these incidents in laboratory settings entails managing water flow rates during drainage and routinely inspecting and tightening hose connections (American Chemical Society [ACS], 2020). By taking these precautions, someone can keep the environment at work safer and avoid any potential risks from water spills.

Significant aspects of risk assessment in occupational safety and health (OSH) are highlighted by the recent incident involving water spilling on the lab floor during the tank filling and drainage stages. Finding possible risks, such as wet and slick floors, which greatly raise the possibility of trips, falls, and slides, requires risk assessment (National Safety Council [NSC], 2021). Risk assessment in OSH entails determining the seriousness of potential outcomes as well as the probability that incidents will occur. Given the serious consequences of a slip or fall injury and the possibility of water leaks from misaligned hoses and excessive drainage flow rates, risk reduction measures are necessary in this

situation. Pre-use assessments to make sure hose connections are tight, instruction on regulated water flow during drainage, and the installation of anti-slip mats to prevent falls are all examples of effective risk reduction. The OSH guidelines, which prioritize hazard identification, risk assessment, and the application of workable solutions to establish safer laboratory environments, are in line with these risk control methods (American Chemical Society [ACS], 2020).

The Hierarchy of Controls in Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) provides an organized method for putting risk-reduction strategies into practice in order to lessen the possibility of water splashing and related risks. Elimination is the first step in the hierarchy; ideally, water-handling procedures should be changed to completely avoid spills, for example, by using automated filling systems that do away with the need for manual adjustments. DOSH Malaysia's 2018 Guidelines for Manual Handling at Workplace place a strong emphasis on the necessity of removing risks related to manual handling duties, especially those brought on by ergonomic concerns. In order to protect employees' health and safety, the rules urge companies to be proactive in detecting and reducing hazards.

Waluś, Warguła, Wieczorek & Krawiec (2022) study offers valuable insights into the slip resistance of various flooring materials in public utility buildings, the wet floor issue remains a significant gap. Since the risk of slipping increases dramatically on wet surfaces, future studies should incorporate tests under both wet and dry conditions to ensure a more accurate understanding of slip resistance. Using more stable or splash-resistant equipment made to reduce water spills could be a substitute if elimination is not practical. Engineering controls are also useful; for instance, putting up barriers or splash guards around drainage and filling areas can assist keep water contained and keep it from getting to the floor. Standard operating procedures (SOPs) for firmly fastening hoses and utilizing slower flow rates during draining are examples of administrative controls. The final line of defense against slip hazards for lab workers is personal protective equipment (PPE), such as footwear that is resistant to slips (National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health [NIOSH], 2021). Each control layer successfully lowers the overall risk of water-related incidents, making the lab environment much safer when this hierarchy is followed.

The Plant Control Systems course will be introduced to final-semester Mechanical Engineering (Plant) diploma students. The control system process, which typically uses water as a fluid medium, is part of several hands-on activities in this course. The observation indicates that the practice of merely disposing of the water used for practical tasks has been ingrained in this laboratory. A substantial amount of wastewater spilled onto the lab floor as a result of the simultaneous processes of filling the tank with water and draining it. There are other concerns in this scenario than water management, which is the possibility of physical hazards when this practical task is implemented. This indicates that addressing the risk of physical hazards and practicing wise water management will be the main goals of this study. As a result, a water reservoir control system will be designed to address safety issues and water management concerns.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Akinwole (2020) study offers a creative and useful approach to water management by thoroughly examining the use of an Arduino microcontroller to automatically regulate tank water levels. The method successfully combines software (algorithm-based coding and simulation using Proteus) and hardware (Arduino and LCD), exhibiting a methodical design and implementation process. Also, Wahyuni, Sentana, Muhandi & Irawan, (2021) emphasises the significance of water management and details the creation of a system that uses an Arduino Uno and ultrasonic sensors to monitor and regulate water levels. This strategy is admirable for resolving issues with conventional

level-switch systems, like frequent pump activation brought on by buoy failures. Utilising cutting-edge technology, like the LM016L LCD and the HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor, shows creativity and usefulness and makes the solution appropriate for a range of uses.

Students can demonstrate the fundamental control theories and concepts of industrial process control systems using the Process Control Trainer Model SE202. The unit is a simplified process model of a typical industrial process that includes batch process control, temperature, and flow. The sump tank needs to be filled with water before this experiment begins. After that, the water can be heated by pumping it around the process rig. The level controller will receive a measurement from a level transmitter that detects the level control tank within. To modify the incoming flow rate to the level control tank, the controller will control the pump speed. Figure 1 shows the unit assembly for the Process Control Trainer. The technique for putting in and removing water from the sump tank is one issue associated with the study's focus. Once the sump tank is filled and emptied, water is simultaneously spilling onto the floor. The physical hazard results from this.

Figure 1. Unit assembly for Process Control Trainer Model SE202.

To ensure continuous operation, the reservoir tank's water level management system must keep the water level constant within a predetermined range. To avoid overflow or depletion, the system should be able to detect and modify water levels with minimal error, keeping an accuracy of ± 1 cm. It must react to changes in water supply or usage quickly—less than five seconds—to modify the water input or outflow as necessary. The system should be able to handle peak inflows without affecting stability and sustain a wide variety of flow rates to meet different operating situations.

It must also deal with access to water, humidity, and temperature changes, making it resilient and dependable in possibly hazardous conditions. To ensure safe operation and avoid equipment damage, safety features such as automatic fault detection, emergency shutoff, and overflow and low-level alerts are crucial. Additionally, the system should be easy to use, with a clear interface for real-time water level and system status monitoring.

To maintain the appropriate water level in a reservoir tank, the water level control system makes use of an Arduino microcontroller, an on/off controller, a pump, and an ultrasonic sensor. Zakamaldin, & Andyk (2014) developed straightforward applications, an autonomous liquid level

control system with a two-position controller and self-regulation is a suitable solution; nevertheless, its stability and performance rely significantly on the controller's adjustment and a thorough analysis of the system dynamics. As seen in Figure 2, the overall system can be made simpler with a block diagram. Positioned at the top of the tank, the ultrasonic sensor measures the distance between itself and the water's surface and instantly converts that measurement into the water level.

Figure 2. Block Diagram for Water Level in the Reservoir Control System.

The Arduino, the central control unit, receives this data from the sensor. The Arduino controls the on/off controller to regulate the pump based on set-up high and low water level limits. The Arduino starts the pump to fill the tank when the water level falls below the lowest threshold and stops it when the water level reaches the upper threshold. This straightforward on/off control method works well for keeping water within the appropriate range and provides an affordable, easy-to-use solution that makes use of the Arduino's programming capabilities for simple calibration and control modifications.

3. FINDINGS

Figure 3 displays a reservoir tank that is intended to be the main source of water for a sump tank in a water delivery system. Adjacent to the reservoir is an on/off control device that enables accurate water flow regulation. Maintaining an effective and long-lasting water level control system is the objective of this configuration. With the reservoir tank serving as the primary supply source, the design may be able to solve issues with water delivery and ensure a steady flow to the sump tank as required. Putting this setup into practice might help find a workable solution for the problems this study covers.

Figure 3. CAD drawing for the reservoir tank.

The reservoir tank is seen in actual use in figure 4(a). A pump that provides water to the sump tank is included in this tank. The controller features two buttons on top that are used to transmit a command to the pump to fill the sump tank and return the water to the reservoir tank. Figure 4(b) illustrates this. To measure the current height of the water level in both tanks, an ultrasonic sensor is affixed to the top of the tank and serves as a detector. The pump will cease supplying water once the specified level is reached.

Figure4(a).

Figure 4(b).

Table 1 distinguishes manual and semi-automated approaches to reservoir filling and emptying. Using the manual method, as seen in figure 5(a), filling and draining take five and six minutes, respectively. As seen in figure 6(a), hazards include a wet floor and a significant likelihood of slipping due to the repetitive task. The semi-automatic approach, on the other hand, significantly reduces filling and draining durations to 1 minute and 38 seconds each, eliminates wet floor hazards, reduces slip hazards, and eliminates repetitive tasks, all of which enhance overall ergonomics. Figure 5(b) and figure 6(b) demonstrate this. The project has resulted in a safer and more effective solution by effectively addressing and resolving the main problems.

Table 1. Result of study

Item(s)	Manual	Semi-Automatic
Filling Time	5 minutes	1 minute 38 second
Drainage Time	6 minutes	1 minute 38 second
Hazard	Wet Floor	No wet floor
Risk Assessment	High to slip	Eliminate risk
Ergonomic	Repetition work	No repetition work

Figure 5(a)

Figure 5(b)

Figure 6(a).

Figure 6(b).

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study effectively addresses important issues related to water management and safety in a laboratory reservoir tank control system. Water spillage and slipping hazards are successfully reduced, filling and draining periods are shortened, and water waste is avoided by putting in place a semi-automated control system. Ultrasonic sensors and an Arduino-based controller work together to enable accurate water level control, which saves resources and improves lab safety in general. This system is a useful tool for both industrial and educational applications since it not only effectively addresses real-world problems that arise in lab settings but also encourages sustainable water use and strengthens a safety culture.

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